

PLANNING STRATEGY ON ADDITIONAL LESSONS TO IMPROVE THE QUALITY OF ISLAMIC RELIGIOUS EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

The planning strategy for additional lessons to improve the quality of Islamic religious education is carried out by providing additional lessons targeted at final class students. Education is not only the responsibility of parents, educational institutions or the government, but a shared responsibility. the strategy and role of the Islamic Religious Education teacher as the most important part of an educational institution, which does not only transfer knowledge but also relates to the values of implementing daily worship, so that teachers are required to be able to choose various kinds of appropriate learning strategies and roles as a competent teacher, thus the goal of improving the quality of student learning can be achieved. Implementation of learning, carried out at times outside of school hours to run effectively. Student achievement after participating in learning that is held outside of school hours is expected to get good and satisfying results. The implementation of learning outside of school hours is expected to be effective and efficient by utilizing students' free time, and to be carried out with a concept and effective time management that does not appear to be forcing students.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Education is something related to human life. Education is also an attempt by adult humans who are aware of their humanity in guiding, training, teaching and instilling the values and basic outlook on life of the younger generation, so that later they become human beings who are aware and responsible for their life tasks as human beings, in accordance with with human nature and characteristics. Education in a general sense includes all the efforts and actions of the older generation to transfer their experience, knowledge, skills and skills to the younger generation to enable them to carry out their life functions in social relations as well as possible (Prasetya, 2000: 13).

Education that takes place both in formal, non-formal or informal institutions, the goal is to make all of their students to be good, to become human beings who are useful for their families, homeland, nation, and religion. Through education, it is hoped that they will become creative, high-disciplined human beings who are ready to use development who will hold the baton to continue the nation's ideals, this is in accordance with SISDIKNAS Law No. 20 of 2003 article 3 (Department of Education and Teaching, 2003: 17).

On the basis of the law above, education has an important role in our lives. With education, we will gain knowledge, thus it will be easier for us to face the era of globalization and overcome the problems that confront us. Through education we are expected to gain useful knowledge that will lead to the goal of good knowledge than before. As disclosed by Yusuf Qhardawi (Yusuf Qhardawi, 1998: 93). that Allah SWT distinguishes

between people who are knowledgeable and people who are not knowledgeable are clearly not the same. What is said in QS. Az-Zumar : 9

"Say, Are there people who know and people who do not know? Indeed, it is people who have sense who can receive lessons" (QS. Az-Zumar: 09).

Through this verse, we can see that it turns out that seeking knowledge is very important in our life. Revealing the problem of education, people assume that education will always be related to the school world that connects teachers and students. However, sometimes people are not aware that before a child becomes a student, the child has received education from his family, especially his father and mother. This family education is very important compared to other education.

Thus education can be formulated as an adult's effort in providing guidance and direction to students towards maturity which is given with a sense of responsibility. In carrying out this education there is a forum or institution that will manage it as previously described above. Students' formal educational institutions will be related to various rules and regulations that apply according to their level of education. This is because educational institutions are regular, systematic, and have a certain timeframe that runs from Kindergarten to Higher Education (Zahara Idris, 1982: 57).

In addition to formal education, there is also education in the community which is unconsciously taking place in everyday life which is called informal education. Because these informal educational institutions take place among families or households and within the community as expressed by Sulaiman Yusuf and Slamet Santoso, they state that informal education is education that is obtained from daily experience consciously or unconsciously from birth to death. in the family, in work or everyday experiences. From this definition it is also said that informal education is an educational institution that takes place simultaneously with the presence of humans and all life. Like a child who has just been born especially for Islamic education, by calling the Adhan or Iqamat in his ear, this education continues until he is an adult. Non-formal education is also very much needed in supporting formal education, this is because the knowledge and knowledge that we get from school is not enough in developing student knowledge. The success of an education is not only learning during school hours, but is also influenced by additional learning, as is the case with additional Islamic education lessons for some students outside of school hours.

In holding additional PAI teaching outside school hours which is held in the afternoon, this is done considering that formal institutions (schools) are not able to fully achieve the expected goals of Islamic education. Therefore non-formal education (additional teaching / tutoring) is expected to be able to help achieve the goal of education, namely to form human beings who have noble character. The additional teaching of Islamic education carried out by several schools is a benchmark for evaluating student learning outcomes in the previous year. This additional teaching program has actually been implemented for a long time. At first this program was devoted to the final class in facing the National Examination.

So, the planning strategy in active learning is a unit, which also includes a comprehensive collection of learning process strategies. Active learning includes a variety of ways to get students active from the start, through activities that lead to group work and in a short or short time make them think about the content of the subject matter. There are also leading learning techniques for all classes, for small groups, in order to be stimulated into a discussion and debate, practicing skills, encouraging questions until finally getting students to teach one another.

2. METHODS

Explaining This study uses qualitative research. namely descriptive research, so that the data collected is in the form of words or pictures. Qualitative research does not generalize but emphasizes the information aspect in the field so that it becomes meaningful. (Sugiyono, 2017) the stages in data collection carried out by researchers are interviews and observations. So that researchers become easily analyze and describe the results of their research. The stages that must be taken in conducting qualitative research are: 1. data reduction; Reducing data means summarizing, choosing the main things, focusing on the important things, and looking for themes and patterns. 2. Presentation of data; After reducing the data, the next step is to present the data. Because it will make it easier for researchers to understand what is going on and then plan further work based on what has been understood. 3. Conclusion drawing/verification; The final stage in analyzing qualitative data is drawing conclusions and verification. The first conclusion made is only temporary and will change if no strong and supporting evidence is found at the next stage of data collection. On the other hand, if the conclusions made at the first stage are supported by concrete and consistent evidence, then the conclusions drawn are conclusions that can be trusted.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Planning Strategy

Meanwhile, Thompson's opinion in Rangka, strategic management refers to process managerial to form a strategic vision, objective preparation, creation on a strategy in realizing and implementing the strategy at all times should make adjustments and corrections to the vision, strategic objectives and implementation of the program. Meanwhile, Ansof in Sagala (2009: 129) explains, Strategic management is a systematic approach to a management responsibility, conditioning the organization to a position that is sure to achieve goals in a way that will ensure sustainable success and make the company (school) guarantee or secure the format which is surprising. So, strategic management is highly demanded in doing so, so that results are realized in all programs set out in strategic planning collectively.

In the context of management, the term strategic can be interpreted as the main ways and tactics that are designed systematically in carrying out management functions that are directed at the strategic goals of the organization. The Strategic includes the process of formulating and implementing plans and activities related to vital, pervasive and sustainable matters for an organization as a whole. Thus strategic management is a set of decisions and actions that result in the formulation (formulation) and implementation (implementation) of plans designed to achieve organizational goals.

Based on historical experience in organizing an organization, the main benefit in applying the principles of strategic management to educational institutions is how to assist educational institutions in formulating strategies that are more effective and efficient by using several approaches, such as a systematic, logical and rational approach to the process selection of education management strategies in the global era which are continuously changing. What forms the basis of strategic management is how to foster a commitment or participation/support from various parties regarding the vision, mission of an educational institution, the focus or goals of providing education, and efforts to achieve it. Based on these,

The positive benefit of strategic management is that it can provide opportunities for an organization in empowering individuals. Empowerment is an action to strengthen the executive's understanding of effectiveness by encouraging and rewarding organizational elements to participate in making decisions and exercising initiative and imagination. The application of strategic management in the administration of systems in educational institutions, enables an educational institution organization (including schools and departments that collaborate or manage educational institutions) to be more proactive in shaping the future of educational institutions in today's globalized world. In applying the concept of thinking and acting strategically, educational institutions are expected to be able to initiate and influence rather than simply responding to demands and routine and bureaucratic activities. However, educational institutions must also be able to work hard in planning strategic activities, implementing and controlling all institutional operations to achieve the strategic goals that have been formulated previously.

2. Additional lessons

Provision of additional lessons given to students in the form of gifts We can categorize additional lessons as a form of out-of-school education. There are several meanings that we can make suggestions about the notion of non-formal education (non-formal education). Non-formal education is an educational activity that is regulated outside the formal education system either running separately or as an important part of a broader activity aimed at serving known student targets and for educational purposes" (M. Sarjan Kadir, 1982:49)

Based on the two definitions above, it can be used as a suggestion to define the notion of education outside of school, especially additional lessons, namely; subjects given to students outside of school, with direction, guidance by adults consciously to students, so that students have characteristics and traits that are in accordance with the ideals of education as a whole so that intellectually good students are formed, emotional and spiritual, it is hoped that through the provision of additional lessons to students it is hoped that they will be able to carry out their duties both for themselves and for other people around them. QThe goals of education that the author has stated above have the goal of wanting Indonesian people to have faith and fear of God Almighty, have noble character and others. This can certainly be realized with a comprehensive education and can be done both formally during school hours and informally outside of school hours by providing additional lessons for students. This is one of the reasons for providing additional lessons to students.

In providing additional lessons the target is students from the final grade. This is evidence and commitment from school administrators and teachers in carrying out national education goals and shared moral responsibility that education is not only the responsibility of parents, educational institutions and the government, but shared responsibility. Implementation of learning, carried out at times outside of school hours so that it runs effectively. Student achievement after participating in learning held outside of school hours is expected to get good and satisfying results. It is hoped that the application of the implementation of learning outside of school hours will run effectively and efficiently by utilizing students' free time, and carried out with

an effective concept and time management and does not appear to be imposing pressure on students. This activity does not have to be carried out every day but only a few days a week, time planning and the use of methods in the learning process that are right on target are highly expected.

3. Quality Education

According to Arcaro, quality is a deep structured process repair output or output generated and based on positive efforts made by individual (Jerome S. Arcaro, 2007: 75). Each individual has a very important role to play produce something positive. Quality assurance is also a way of producing products that are free from deficiencies and errors and consistently fulfilling product specifications or also producing products that are always effective and efficient from the start and are carried out to satisfy education connoisseurs. The reference for quality to be used as the attainment or fulfillment of educational quality in educational institutions is the National Education Standards (SNP) and other standards that have been agreed upon by educational observer groups. National education standards are standards made by the central and regional governments, while other standards are standards made by an educational institution or other institution which is used as a reference by educational institutions.

National Education Standards or SNP are the minimum criteria regarding the education system throughout the territory of the Republic of Indonesia, that Government Regulation Number 19 of 2005 concerning National Education Standards needs to be adjusted or harmonized with the dynamics of community development, locally, nationally, and globally so that the functions and objectives of national education can be realized, the government issues a Government Regulation as an amendment to PP No. 19 of 2005. The PP is PP No. 32 of 2013.

4. Islamic Education

According to Zakiah Drajat, religious education concerns the whole human being, it does not only equip children with religious knowledge or develops children's intellects and does not only fill or nourish religious feelings (sentiments), but concerns the whole child's personality, starting with exercises (amaliah). related to and in accordance with the contents of religious teachings, both human relations with the Creator, humans with other humans, or humans with the universe and humans with their own individuals. Zakiah Drajat, 1970: 107). Thus religious education is obtained by children from the family, school, and community environment where they associate so that they have a knowledge and experience that is useful for themselves and is able to practice it, thus this religious education will shape the whole human personality.

Islamic education is an education that gives awareness and has a purpose or purpose. Allah has also arranged a clear foundation in education for all mankind through the rules in Islamic law. The concept of height and universality of Islamic education must be understood before we move on to the methods and characteristics of this education. In interpreting the purpose of life, humans are given the opportunity according to the time limit set by God through the destruction of this worldly life. From there, God made humans and the universe as new creatures who were then brought to account and rewarded according to their deeds. Allah will repay disbelief with hell and goodness with eternal pleasure. Education in Islam places great emphasis on individual and social management which can lead followers to fully and comprehensively realize Islamic values. In order for its adherents to be able to carry out the mandate desired by Allah, Islamic education must be interpreted in detail. Therefore, the existence of references or sources of Islamic education must be the main source of Islam itself, namely the Qur'an and As-Sunnah. forward Islamic values.

4. CONCLUSION

Strategy planning in additional lessons to improve the quality of Islamic religious education is carried out by providing additional lessons which are the target of students from the final grade. This is evidence and commitment from school administrators and teachers in carrying out national education goals and shared moral responsibility that education is not only the responsibility of parents, educational institutions and the government, but a shared responsibility. Implementation of learning, carried out at times outside of school hours so that it runs effectively. Student achievement after participating in learning held outside of school hours is expected to get good and satisfying results. It is hoped that the application of the implementation of learning outside of school hours will run effectively and efficiently by utilizing students' free time, and carried out with an effective concept and time management and does not appear to be imposing pressure on students. This activity does not have to be carried out every day but only a few days a week, time planning and the use of methods in the learning process that are right on target are highly expected..

According to the author, the method in additional lessons in Islamic education is to collaborate with various methods, according to the existing situations and conditions. Providing additional Islamic Religious Education (PAI) lessons covering the study of the Qur'an, Jurisprudence, Hadith, Adab and the practice of

worship, tahfizh as well as calligraphy and prayers. The role of Islamic Religious Education (PAI) supplementary lessons in the formation of student morals is greatly felt by the children themselves, parents and society as a whole if it can be carried out effectively and efficiently. Therefore, it can be understood that the evaluation of teaching and learning outcomes carried out by teachers in Islamic religious education consists of formative evaluations and summative evaluations. This formative evaluation is used to determine the extent to which students' abilities have been achieved and to determine the teacher's success in presenting lessons and also aims to shape student personality. This summative evaluation aims to determine students' ability to master the material that has been given by the teacher for one semester. Giving this summative evaluation is usually carried out at the end of the teaching program carried out at the end of the semester.

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- a. Providing additional lessons carried out in order to adapt to the circumstances of the students.
- b. To the elements in charge of educational institutions to be able to prepare teaching staff who are really ready intellectually, morally and in aqidah so that they are able to become *qudwah* (models) for their students
- c. To parents, scholars and community leaders around educational institutions to work together with administrators of educational institutions so that additional learning programs can run effectively and efficiently.

There is a need for donor support to support the continuation of additional Islamic religious education activities which can be obtained from donations from the government, parents and the surrounding community so that the implementation of these activities can run optimally.

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